

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/308765184>

Physics-Based Analysis of the Base Transit Time in SiGe-HBT with Gaussian Doped Base

Article · August 2014

CITATIONS

2

READS

128

4 authors:

Sm Islam

Lumiode Inc.

51 PUBLICATIONS 1,072 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Iqbal Bahar Chowdhury

United International University

66 PUBLICATIONS 140 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Yeasir Arafat

Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology

32 PUBLICATIONS 95 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Md. Ziaur Rahman Khan

Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology

121 PUBLICATIONS 927 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

PHYSICS-BASED ANALYSIS OF THE BASE TRANSIT TIME IN SIGE-HBT WITH GAUSSIAN DOPED BASE

S. M. Moududul Islam,
University of Notre Dame, USA
SM.M.Islam.2@nd.edu

Md. IqbalBaharChowdhury
United International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
ibchy@eee.uui.ac.bd

Yeasir Arafat and Md. ZiaurRahman Khan
Bangladesh University of Engineering Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract:

Base transit time for an npnSiGe heterojunction bipolar transistor with Gaussian base doping profile has been assessed and analyzed based on physics. Non-ideal effects such as Band-gap narrowing (BGN), doping dependence of carrier mobility, velocity-saturation at the base-collector junction and carrier and electric field modulation due to high-injection level have been considered in the work. In order to incorporate the effects of Germanium (Ge) content on the BGN and saturation velocity, a generalized profile for Ge mole fraction distribution is used, where Ge profile variation has been illustrated by varying a single parameter for box, trapezoidal and triangular forms. The results show that the derived analytical model can provide more insight behind the physics of the base transit time for SiGe-HBT.

Key words: energy efficient building, natural ventilation, air circulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Heterojunction Bipolar Transistors (HBTs) are more advantageous than their homojunction counterparts for their reduced lateral base resistance, improved unity-gain-bandwidth frequency, improved high frequency response, reduced emitter current crowding, increased noise figure etc. Although there are different III-V HBTs, SiGe-base HBTs are proved to be their efficient alternative [1, 2]. Due to Ge-presence in the base region the bandgap narrowing in the base can be made lower for SiGe-HBT than that in Silicon BJT [3].

Although the introduction of Ge leads to a strained SiGe base layer, the strain is tolerable if the layer thickness is less than a critical value [4]. Further improvements in device performance can be achieved by introducing a compositional grading in the base region. In fact, the base grading creates a drift field which sweeps the electrons towards the collector. Due to the high speed performance and mature silicon process, SiGe HBTs have emerged as the technology of

choice for the Radio Frequency Integrated Circuits (RFICs) [5].

Base transit time plays a very crucial role in determining the high frequency performance of a transistor, as it is more than 70% of a bipolar transistor's total transit time [6]. However, a number of non-ideal effects are present that affects the base transit time; these effects include bandgap narrowing effects due to heavy doping and presence of Ge, doping dependence of carrier mobility, carrier and field modulation due to high injection level and modification in the saturation velocity at the base collector junction due to Ge-content in the base region etc. Therefore, a number of transit time models of SiGe HBTs have been proposed in the literature [6-15] which tried to include these effects as much as possible in their models to accurately explain the physics behind the base transit time. Owing to the inherent mathematical complexity, most of these models employed numerical methods to calculate the base transit time. Basu [11] developed an analytical model for the base transit time considering the doping dependence of the bandgap narrowing effect. Arafat et al. [13], in their model, included doping and field dependence of the carrier mobility too; but the base doping profile is exponential in their model. For the Gaussian doped base, S. M. M. Islam et al. developed an analytical model under low injection level condition in [14] and extended their model to high-injection level condition in [15]. Although the later model [15] did the mathematics of the model, the physics was not explained therein. This work is, therefore, aimed to focus on the physical insight of the base transit time considering all the non-ideal effects mentioned earlier.

In Section 2, the mathematical modeling developed in [15] is reviewed, with due emphasis given on the physics. Section 3 presents the results starting from the electron concentration in the base, so that a gradual understanding of the physics can be developed. Discussions on the results and comparisons with other models are also presented in this section. The

concluding remarks finally come into conclusion section.

II. ANALYSIS

For HBT, the base transit time can be found by using the following relation [16]

$$\tau_B = q \int_0^{W_B} \frac{n(x)}{J_n(x)} dx \quad (1)$$

where $n(x)$ is the minority carrier concentration and $J_n(x)$ is the electron current density within the base, q is the charge of an electron. For the base region, $n(x)$ can be found using the transport equation and electric field equation given below [17]

$$-J_n = qn(x)\mu_n(x)E(x) + qD_n(x) \frac{dn(x)}{dx} \quad (2)$$

$$E(x) = \frac{kT}{q} \left\{ \frac{1}{p(x)} \frac{dp(x)}{dx} - \frac{1}{n_{ie}^2(x)} \frac{dn_{ie}^2(x)}{dx} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where D_n (D_p) is the electron (hole) diffusivity, μ_n (μ_p) is the electron (hole) mobility respectively, $E(x)$ is the electric field, $p(x)$ is the hole concentration and $n_{ie}(x)$ is the effective intrinsic carrier concentration. J_n in (2) is defined such that it has a positive value. As the base width of today's high-speed HBT is less than 100 nm (even 26 nm base width is used in literature [9]), so the carrier recombination in the base region can safely be neglected, resulting in a constant J_n which finally equals to the collector current J_C . In this entire derivation process, the minority carrier concentration at thermal equilibrium has been neglected. Neglecting majority hole current in the base (J_p) and using (2), (3) along with Einstein's relation [$D_n/\mu_n = D_p/\mu_p = kT/q$], the total current density becomes

$$-J_n = qD_n(x) \frac{n_{ie}^2(x)}{n(x) + N_B(x)} \times \frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{n(x)\{n(x) + N_B(x)\}}{n_{ie}^2(x)} \right] \quad (4)$$

where locally valid quasi charge neutrality approximation [$p(x) \approx n(x) + N_A(x)$] is used. The solution of Eqn. (4) needs the physical models for Bandgap narrowing models (n_{ie}) that includes both the effect of heavy doping levels and the Ge content, doping dependence of the carrier mobility (μ_n) along with the effect of Ge content, velocity saturation models considering the presence of the Ge content and also, the shape of the doping profile and the Ge dosing profile. Moreover, effect of injection level on the electric field need to be considered to extend the solution applicable to all injection levels.

II.A. DOPING, DOSING PROFILES

The Base doping profile used in this analysis is Gaussian and given by

$$N_B(x) = N_B(0)e^{-mx^2} \quad (5)$$

where, $N_B(0)$ is the peak base doping concentration (at $x = 0$), $m = \frac{1}{2\sigma^2}$, $\sigma = \frac{W_B}{\sqrt{\{2 \ln \left[\frac{N_B(0)}{N_B(W_B)} \right] \}}}$ and $N_B(W_B)$ is the

doping concentration at $x=W_B$.

Three different dosing (mole fraction distribution profiles) $y(x)$ as shown in Fig.1 are used in this work. For a trapezoidal profile, y can be expressed as a function of distance (x) along the neutral base width (W_B) as

$$y(x) = m_{Ge}x + y_E \quad (6)$$

where $m_{Ge} = (y_C - y_E)/W_B$ and y_C (y_E) is the Ge fraction at the collector (emitter). Eqn. (6) represents triangular profile for $y_E = 0$ and represents box shape profile for $y_E = y_C$ [8]. Total Ge content within the base is called Ge dose and is calculated as [9] $y_D = y_{av}W_B$ where $y_{av} = (y_C + y_E)/2$.

Fig 1 Distribution of Ge content in Si on emitter side

B. PHYSICAL MODELS

The low-field doping dependent electron diffusivity in the presence of Ge, $D_{n,SiGe}$ can be related with that in Si, $D_{n,Si}$ as [7]

$$D_{n,SiGe} = bD_{n,Si} \quad (7)$$

where $b = 1 + 3y_{av}$ and $D_{n,Si}$ is well approximated as [18]

$$\mu_{n0} = \frac{D_n(0)}{kT} \left(\frac{N_A(x)}{N_{m,ref}} \right)^{-\gamma_1} \quad (8)$$

With $D_n(0) = 20.72 \text{ cm}^2 (\text{V}\cdot\text{s})^{-1}$, $N_{m,ref} = 1.0 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $\gamma_1 = 0.42$. The saturation velocity inside the SiGe alloy also differs from that in Si as [19] $v_{s,SiGe} = Cv_{s,Si}$ with C given by

$$C = \frac{0.342}{0.342 + y_{av}(1 - y_{av})} \quad (9)$$

The effective intrinsic carrier concentration in SiGe is given by

$$n_{ie,SiGe}^2 = \gamma_r n_{io,Si}^2 e^{\frac{\Delta E_{gHD}(x) + \Delta E_{gGe}(x)}{kT}} \quad (10)$$

$$\gamma_r = e^{-sqr5 y_{av}} \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta E_{gHD}(x) = qV_{gHD} \ln \left(\frac{N_A}{N_{ref}} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta E_{gGe}(x) = qV_{gGe} \gamma(x) \quad (13)$$

where γ_r is the ratio of the effective density of states in SiGe to that in Si given by [7, 12], ΔE_{gHD} is the bandgap narrowing due to heavy doping effects modeled by [20, 21] and ΔE_{gGe} is the bandgap narrowing due to presence of Ge which is assumed to have a linear dependence on Ge concentration [16] with $n_{i0} = 1.194 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_{ref} = 1.3 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $V_{gHD} = 13.8 \text{ mV}$ and $V_{gGe} = 688 \text{ mV}$. Combining the Eqns. (10) to (13) for the Gaussian doping profile gives

$$n_{ie,SiGe}^2(x) = n_{ie,SiGe}^2(0) e^{m_3 x - m_2 x^2} \quad (14)$$

where

$$n_{ie,SiGe}^2(0) = n_{i0,Si}^2 \gamma_r e^{\gamma_3 y_E} \left[\frac{N_B(x)}{N_r} \right]^{\gamma_2} \quad (15)$$

$$\gamma_2 = \frac{V_{gHD}}{V_T}, \quad \gamma_3 = \frac{V_{gGe}}{V_T}, \quad V_T = \frac{kT}{q}, \quad m_2 = m\gamma_2$$

and $m_3 = m_{Ge}\gamma_3$.

C. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The solution of the differential Eqn. needs two boundary conditions, namely, at $x = 0$ i.e. at the base-emitter junction and at $x = W_B$ i.e. at the base-collector junction. At $x=0$, the electron concentration can be found by using the following relation [22] with necessary correction for SiGe

$$n(0) = \frac{n_{ie,SiGe}^2(0)}{N_A(0)} e^{\frac{V_{BE}}{V_T}} f_w \quad (16)$$

where

$$f_w = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} + \left[\frac{N_A(0)}{n_{ie,SiGe}(0)} \right]^2 e^{\frac{V_{BE}}{V_T}}}} \quad (17)$$

Though Suzuki [22] used this boundary condition for high injection region considering Webster effect [23], it is also valid for low injection, as the value of f_w becomes unity for $V_{BE} \leq 0.75 \text{ V}$.

Since the electron velocity is assumed to be saturated at the saturation velocity [24] at $x = W_B$, another boundary condition can be obtained by relating the electron current density (J_n) with the electron concentration ($n(W_B)$) as

$$J_n = qv_{s,SiGe} n(W_B) \quad (18)$$

D. MODEL DERIVATION

For low injection (LI) condition [$n(x) \ll N_B(x)$], the quasi-neutral condition becomes $p(x) \approx N_B(x)$. Therefore, the electric field $E(x)$ and minority electron

current density J_n for low level of injection can be written as

$$E_{SiGe}(x) = -V_T (m_3 + m_4 x) \quad (19)$$

$$-J_n = qD_{nl,SiGe}(x) \frac{n_{ie,SiGe}^2(x)}{N_B(x)} \times \frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{n_l(x) N_B(x)}{n_{ie,SiGe}^2(x)} \right] \quad (20)$$

where $m_4 = 2(m - m_2)$. Using the expressions $n_{ie,SiGe}^2(x)$, $N_B(x)$ and $D_{nl,SiGe}(x)$ in Eqn. (20), the first order differential equation for minority carrier concentration $n_l(x)$ can be written as

$$\frac{dn_l(x)}{dx} - (m_4 x + m_3) n_l(x) = -\frac{J_n}{qbD_{nl}} e^{-m_1 x^2} \quad (21)$$

The solution of this equation gives

$$n_l(x) = e^{\frac{m_4 x^2}{2} + m_3 x} [n_l(0) - J_n B(x)] \quad (22)$$

$$J_n = A_{low} n_l(0) \quad (23)$$

where $n_l(0)$ is the LI value of $n(0)$,

$$B(x) = A \left[\sqrt{\pi} \frac{p}{m_3} e^{p^2} \left\{ \text{erf} \left(p + \frac{x}{\sqrt{m_4 + 2m_1}} \right) - \text{erf}(p) \right\} \right]$$

$$A = \frac{1}{qbD_{nl}}, \quad p = \frac{m_3}{\sqrt{2m_4 + 4m_1}}$$

$$A_{low} = \frac{e^{\frac{m_4 W_B^2}{2} + m_3 W_B}}{\frac{1}{qv_{sA}} + B(W_B) e^{\frac{m_4 W_B^2}{2} + m_3 W_B}}$$

The base stored charge per unit area is given by

$$Q_{Bnl} = q \int_0^{W_B} n_l(x) dx \quad (24)$$

Using Eqn. (23) and Eqn. (24), Eqn. (1) [the equation for the base transit time under LI condition] becomes

$$\tau_{Bl} = \frac{Q_{Bnl}}{J_n} \quad (25)$$

Now, the analysis for low injection can be extended to incorporate moderate level of injection with slight modification using perturbation theory [25]. The modified carrier concentration and current density for moderate injection can be given by

$$n_m(x) = n_l(x) f_w \quad (26)$$

$$J_n = J_{nl} f_w \quad (27)$$

Here f_w is used to incorporate Webster effect [23]. Assuming that the injected electron concentration is perturbed by the modulated electric field from $n_m(x)$ only a little and also using quasi-neutrality of charge

equation, $n(x)$ and $p(x)$ for moderate injection can be found as below

$$n(x) = n_m(x) + \delta n(x) \quad (28)$$

$$p(x) = n_m(x) + \delta n(x) + N_B(x) \approx n_m(x) + N_B(x) \quad (29)$$

where for the accuracy of derivation, the deviation $\delta n(x)$ must be $\ll n_m(x) + N_B(x)$ instead of $\ll n_m(x)$. Now, following the same procedure as low injection, Eqn. (4) can be solved to find $n(x)$ for moderate injection

$$n(x) = \frac{e^{m_3x - m_2x^2}}{p(x)} \left[n(0)p(0) + \frac{J_n}{qv_{s, SiGe}} N(x) \right] \quad (30)$$

where

$$N(x) = -\frac{v_{sA}}{bD_n} \{n_m(0)E_1(x) + N_B(0)E_3(x) - J_{nm}E_2(x) - E_0\}$$

$$\int e^{m_5x^2} dx = E_1(x) + D_1$$

$$\int B(x)e^{m_5x^2} dx = E_2(x) + D_2$$

$$\int e^{-m_3x - m_6x^2} dx = E_3(x) + D_3$$

with $m_5 = m - m_1$, $m_6 = m_4/2 + m_1$ and $E_0 = n_m(0)E_1(0) + N_B(0)E_3(0) - J_{nm}E_2(0)$. Using the boundary condition at $x = W_B$, J_n can be determined. This J_n then can be used to calculate the total base stored charge Q_{Bn} and the base transit time τ_B .

E. PHYSICS BASED ANALYSIS

Modern BJTs need to work with higher current levels to meet the industry demand and hence, need to work with higher bias levels; but, high injection effects, which cause BJTs performance to degrade severely and hence, should be avoided, become significant as bias level increases. The onset of the high injection effects, commonly referred to as the Kirk effect [26], can be moved further in bias by applying heavier doping level in the base. But due to heavier doping level electron mobility in the base decreases. As a result, electrons in the base needs longer time to traverse the base region i.e. the base transit time increases.

Since the base transit time is the most dominant component of total transit time of a BJT, the high frequency performance measures such as cutoff frequency, noise figure and maximum frequency of operation of today's BJT are strongly influenced by the base transit time. Therefore, the scientists and engineers are constantly looking for a way to reduce this transit time so that high frequency performance of the BJT can be improved. This reduction can be achieved if electron concentration in the base can be reduced or if the electron current in the base can be increased or both. An electric field introduced in the base in the direction of current flow can do the both; it can sweep the electrons from the base very quickly causing the electrons to

decrease in the base as well as the electron current to increase. Instead of using uniform doping profile throughout the base, a non-uniform doping profile (a decaying profile for the p-type base of an npn transistor) creates an electric field exactly in the direction of the current flow. The strength of the field depends on the gradient of the electron concentration, gradient of the doping density and the gradient of the band structure [27].

However, owing to the heavier and non-uniform doping levels, the band structure becomes position dependent [27]. This position dependence of the band structure not only makes the bandgap narrowing effects to be significant, but also creates an electric field, which works in the opposite direction of the current flow. Therefore, the increase in the effective electric field acting on the electrons in the base region is somewhat less and hence, the reduction of the base transit time is not significant. This is even worse when injection level increases, since with increasing injection levels the concentration of electrons in the base region increases; that is the electron concentration gradient and hence, the electric field decreases as injection level increases.

Since BJTs with high current capabilities uses heavy base doping level as mentioned earlier, these BJTs suffer severe degradation in the high frequency performance, especially, in the high current regime. In order to alleviate the degradation of the high frequency performance, the opposing effect of bandgap narrowing on the electric field need to be lessened. In this respect, Ge dosing comes into the scenario as the presence of Ge content may aid or retard the bandgap narrowing depending on the gradient of the dosing profile.

The non-uniform base doping profile has a negative gradient to create an electric field in the negative direction (in the direction of the current flow); this doping profile, therefore, causes the band structure in the base to increase in the positive direction (i.e. band structure increases from the emitter side to the collector side) and hence, creates an electric field in the positive direction. If the gradient of the Ge dosing profile is positive, the band structure in the base region then starts decreasing from the emitter side to the collector side owing to the presence of the Ge content and hence, an electric field is created in the negative direction, thereby, aiding the effective field acting on the electrons. This means that the box dosing profile adds nothing and the trapezoidal dosing adds a moderate contribution, whereas, the triangular dosing adds the largest contribution to the effective electric field. Therefore, the largest base transit time will be expected for the box dosing profile, whereas, the minimum will be expected for triangular profile.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section the results of the proposed model are presented and analyzed. The base width of the SiGe-HBT is chosen as 100 nm. The shape of Ge dosing profile has significant effect on the electric field in the

base. This effect is shown in Fig. 2. The figure shows that the electric field is the largest for the triangular dosing profile, whereas it is the lowest for the box profile. This is obvious due to the fact that the slope of the triangular profile is the highest and that of the box profile is the least, as explained in Section II. E.

Fig 2 Electric Field in the base for different shape of Ge profiles

Electric field present in the base sweep out the minority electrons in the base to the collector. The increase in this field is, therefore, results in decrease in the minority electrons storage and the associated increase in the minority electron current density in the base. These results are seen in Figs 3 and 4. As expected, the lowest and the highest minority carrier concentrations are observed (Fig 3) for the triangular dosing profile and the box profile, respectively. For the similar reasoning, the current density is the highest for the triangular profile and is the lowest for the box profile (Fig. 4).

Fig 3 Minority electron concentration in the base for different shape of Ge profiles

Fig4 Minority Electron current density in the base for different shape of Ge profiles

Minority carrier current density J_n is a function of base emitter voltage (V_{BE}). This relation is plotted in Fig 5 for different shape of Ge profiles. For triangular Ge profile, J_n increases with V_{BE} maintaining a constant logarithmic slope but for the other two shapes (trapezoidal and box), the slope of the curves decreases after $V_{BE} = 0.7$ V. J_n for box shape Ge (zero gradient) is higher than that of triangular profile (maximum gradient) and J_n for trapezoidal profile (moderate gradient) remains in-between. This is due to the fact that the current gain in the SiGe HBT is maximum for the box-type profile and minimum for the triangular profile [4].

Fig 5 Current densities vs. base-emitter voltage for different shape of Ge profiles

Fig6 Base transit time vs. base-emitter voltage for different shape of Ge profiles

Base transit time for an npnSiGe base HBT has been calculated for Gaussian doped base and trapezoidal Ge profile under moderate injection. Changing the value of y_E , triangular or box Ge effects are incorporated. The results are shown in Fig 6 which illustrates the plots of τ_B as a function of V_{BE} , for different shape of Ge profiles. For triangular profile, τ_B becomes smaller and remains almost constant but for the other two shapes (trapezoidal and box) τ_B starts to increase after 0.73 V and 0.65 V respectively. Box shape Ge takes higher transit time than triangular to pass the electron to the collector and the trapezoidal Ge takes in-between time as expected from the analysis in Section II.E. This result is also validated by [4] which show that transit through the base is the minimum when the triangular Ge profile is chosen.

The base transit time of a graded base SiGe heterojunction bipolar transistor, calculated using the present model for Gaussian doping profile is compared with uniform doping profile [7] and exponential doping profile [13] in Fig (7). It shows that, Gaussian doped base (considering the same boundary conditions of base doping as in [13]) HBT produces transit times that lie in between the base transit times of uniform and exponential doped base HBTs.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work a physics-based analysis of the base transit time is presented. The base transit time is calculated for a SiGe HBT with Gaussian doped base employing a general type of trapezoidal Ge profile. The transit time is found to be dependent on the type of Ge mole fraction distribution in the base as well as the type of base doping profile. The transit time decreases as the type of trapezoidal Ge profile is changed from box to triangular type. On the other hand, the highest transit time is found with uniformly doped base and the lowest comes up with exponentially doped base for similar boundary conditions. Gaussian doped base HBT produces intermediate base transit time.

Fig 7 Base transit time vs peak Ge fraction in the SiGe HBT with a base width of 45 nm. The Ge profile is triangular with $y_E = 0$. The peak doping concentration in the base is $8 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Base doping profiles are

uniform, exponential-shape with $\eta = 3.5$ [13] and Gaussian-shape with same boundary conditions as exponential doping.

REFERENCE

- [1] Zerounian N., Aniel F., Barbalat B., Chevalier P., and Chantre A., 500 GHz cutoff frequency SiGe HBTs, *Electronics Letters*, vol. 43, pp. 774-775, 2007.
- [2] Xu Z., Niu G., Luo L., Chakraborty P. S., Cheng P., Thomas D., and Cressler J. D., Cryogenic RF Small-Signal Modeling and Parameter Extraction of SiGe HBTs, *IEEE Topical Meeting on Silicon Monolithic Integrated Circuits in RF Systems, SiRF'09*, pp. 1-4, 2009.
- [3] Das M. K., Das N. R., and Basu P. K., Effect of Ge content and profile in the SiGe base on the performance of a SiGe/Si HBT, *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 47, pp. 247-254, 2005.
- [4] Jain S. C., *Germanium-Silicon Strained Layers and Heterostructures*, Academic Press, Inc. USA, 1994.
- [5] Lee K., Cho D. H., Park K. W., and Kim B., Improved VBIC Model for SiGe HBTs With a Unified Model of Heterojunction Barrier Effects, *IEEE Tran. on Electron Devices*, vol. 53(4), p. 743, 2006.
- [6] Mandal S. K., Marskole G. K., Chari K. S., and Maiti C. K., Transit time components of a SiGe-HBT at low temperature, *Proc. 24th International Conference on Microelectronics, Nis, Serbia and Montenegro*, pp. 315-318, 2004.
- [7] Patri V. S. and Kumar M. J., Profile Design Considerations for minimizing base transit time in SiGe HBT's, *IEEE Trans. on Electron Devices*, vol. 45, pp. 1725-1731, 1998.
- [8] Tang Z. R., Kamins T., and Salama C. A. T., Analytical and experimental characteristics of SiGe HBT with thin α -Si : H emitters", *Solid-State Electron.*, vol. 38, pp. 1829-1834, 1995.
- [9] Kwok K. H. and Selvakumar C. R., Profile design considerations for minimizing base transit time in SiGe HBTs for all levels of Injection before onset of Kirk effect, *IEEE Tran. on Electron Devices*, vol. 48, pp. 1540-1549, 2001.
- [10] Poortmans J., Jain S. C., Totterdell D. H. J., Caymax M., Nijs J. F., Mertens R. P., and van Overstraeten R. J., Theoretical calculations and experimental evidence of the real and apparent band gap narrowing due to heavy doping in p type Si and strained $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$ layers, *Solid-State Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 12, pp. 1763-1767, 1993.
- [11] Basu S., Analytical Modeling of Base Transit Time of SiGe HBTs Including Concentration Dependent Bandgap Narrowing Effect, *Journal of Electronic Science and Technology*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 140-143, 2010.

- [12] Zareba A., Lukasiak L., and Jakubowski A., Modeling of SiGe-base heterojunction bipolar transistor with gaussian doping distribution, *Solid-State Electron.*, vol. 45, pp. 2029-2032, 2001.
- [13] Arafat Y., Khan M. Z. R. and Hassan M. M. S., Analytical Modeling of Base Transit Time for a Si_{1-x}Ge_x Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor, *IEEE International Conference of Electron Devices and Solid-State Circuits, EDSSC 2009*, Xi'an, China, pp. 358-361, 2009.
- [14] Islam S. M. M., Chowdhury M. I. B., Arafat Y., Khan M. Z. R. and Hassan M. M. S., Base Transit Time of a Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor with Gaussian Doped Base, *IEEE International Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering, ICECE 2010*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, pp. 127-130, 2010.
- [15] Islam S. M. M., Chowdhury M. I. B., Arafat Y. and Khan M. Z. R., Base Transit Time of a Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor (HBT) with Gaussian Doped Base Under High-Level of Injection, *IEEE International Conference on Devices, Circuits and Systems, ICDCS 2012*, Coimbatore, India, pp. 114-118, 2012.
- [16] Kroemer H., Two integral relations pertaining to electron transport through a bipolar transistor with a nonuniform energy gap in the base region, *Solid-State Electron.*, vol. 28, pp. 1101-1103, 1985.
- [17] van J. S., Effect of base profile on the base transit time of the bipolar transistor for all levels of injection, *IEEE Trans. on Electron Devices*, vol. 41, pp. 212-216, 1994.
- [18] Suzuki K., Optimum base doping profile for minimum base transit time considering velocity saturation at base-collector junction and dependence of mobility and bandgap narrowing on doping concentration, *IEEE Tran. on Electron Devices*, vol. 48, pp. 2102-2107, 2001.
- [19] Chang S. T., Liu C. W., and Lu S. C., Base transit time of graded base Si/SiGe HBTs considering recombination lifetime and velocity saturation, *Solid-State Electron.*, vol. 48, pp. 207-215, 2004.
- [20] Klaassen D. B. M., Slotboom J. W. and de Graaff H. C., Unified apparent bandgap narrowing in n- and p-type Silicon, *Solid State Electron.*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 125-129, 1992.
- [21] Lu T. C. and Kuo J. B., A closed form analytical BJT forward transit time model considering bandgap narrowing effects and concentration dependent diffusion coefficients, *Solid-State Electron.*, vol. 35, pp. 1374-1377, 1992.
- [22] Suzuki K., Analytical base transit time model of uniformly-doped base bipolar transistors for high-injection regions, *Solid-State Electron.*, vol. 36, pp. 109-110, 1993.
- [23] Webster W., On the variation of junction-transistor current amplification factor with emitter current, *Proc IRE*, vol. 42(6), pp. 914-920, 1954.
- [24] Roulston, D. J., Early voltage in very-narrow-base bipolar transistors, *IEEE Electron Device Lett.*, vol. EDL-11, no. 2, pp. 88-89, 1990.
- [25] Hassan M. M. S. and Nomani M. W. K., Base transit time model considering field dependent mobility for BJTs operating at high-level injection, *IEEE Tran. on Electron Devices*, vol. 53, pp. 2532-2539, 2006.
- [26] Kirk C. T., A theory of transistor cutoff frequency (f_T) falloff at high current densities, *IRE Trans. Electron Devices*, vol. ED-9, pp. 164-174, 1962.
- [27] van Overstraeten R. J., Deman H. J. and Mertens R. P., Transport equations in heavy doped silicon, *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices*, vol. ED-20, no. 3, pp. 290-298, 1973.